

E-LICENSE SYSTEM WITH RTO CONTROL ROOM MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT:

Driving license system is a very difficult task for the government to monitor. In this project, all the citizens' images will scan and recorded. Whenever a citizen crosses the traffic rules, the police can scan his image and can check the license through finger. Again with the help of the GPS connected to the RTO Unit the exact Location of the Traffic police will be located in the Control Room. This biometric based driving license monitoring system is very easy and convenient to monitor.

I. INTRODUCTION:

As computer has grown increasingly important in today's society more and more existing products are using computer technology. To modify the partial manual existing system to a more user friendly automated system. In smart E-license system is concerned with RTO system interface with existing system with maximum accuracy. This project is useful for those who have forgotten their license or lost their license under some circumstances this project is applicable. Due to this system the corruption can be routed away from the government system. In Smart E-License system which will be carried by traffic police which includes finger print module along with GSM module. Whenever traffic police wants to check license of someone he/she will take impressions of thumb which consequences request in terms of message to RTO OFFICE then details of person will be provided by RTO to traffic police so that he can check for valid driver. With this system Control Room will be able to track the location of the Traffic police and can make a effective communication.

PURPOSE:

1. Finger Should act as a License
2. No Need to Carry the license

3. Should be a user friendly System
4. Should have centralized database System should be user friendly.

OTHER INFORMATION:

- Driving license system is a very difficult task for the government to monitor.
- In this project, all the citizens' images will scan and recorded. Whenever a citizen crosses the traffic rules, the police can scan his image and can check the license through finger.
- Again with the help of the GPS connected to the RTO Unit the exact Location of the Traffic police will be located in the Control Room .
- This biometric based driving license monitoring system is very easy and convenient to monitor.

II .LITERATURE SURVEY:

Driving license system is a very difficult task for the government to monitor. In this project, all the citizens' images will scan and recorded. Whenever a citizen crosses the traffic rules, the police can scan his image and can check the license through finger. Again with the help of the GPS connected to the RTO Unit the exact Location of the Traffic police will be located in the Control Room. This biometric based driving license monitoring system is very easy and convenient to monitor.

DRAWBACKS IN EXISTING SYSTEM:

Complicated process for getting the License, Time Consuming Process We get a physical copy Paper or smart card', Every time the License Paper / Smart card need to carry, No any Centralized Database for verifying the license so for each state and internally for each district separate offices maintains the database. Corruption chances are there Problem of physical license/ Smart card damaged or lost

At the current situation license is must when a person drive and forgot his/her license. When any person is driving a vehicle it is must that he/she carries all the required documents regarding the RTO. But when traffic police check these documents that person may fail to carry all of them or their may be some happenings with that document unfortunately. As the traffic increases the need of RTO and license requirement also increases so it becomes very difficult to make a new license when any people lose the license. While considering the Indian situation the corruption can be rooted out from the government system. Due to this system citizens do not have to bare this entire problem. When that person gives a genuine reason for he/she not carrying the document he/she have to pay the fine to the traffic police.

III.IMPLIMENTATION:

IMPLIMENTATION DETAILS:

To implement this new E-license system uses ARM-7, finger print module along with GSM module, GSM module one for transmitter and one for receiver. In this system the device which will carry by traffic police consist ARM, GSM and finger print module. Whenever traffic police wants to check license of someone he will take thumb impression as finger print module. This finger print senses module with TTL UART interface for direct connection to ARM controls UART RTO PC through GSM transmitter. GMS and ARM control are connected to each other by max232. The receiver GSM having a unique identification number is get verified with RTO database system. The database is created with the help of Microsoft access and it is interfaced with visual basic through program. If RTO database is match with transmitter GSM and it will displayed on LCD the person is valid or invalid. The database of RTO office counts the number of valid or invalid users. In addition to this system, alcohol detection is also possible. Whenever traffic police wants to check license of person, simultaneous he will check person is drunk or not.

BLOCK DIAGRAM:

TRAFFIC POLICE SYSTEM:

The block diagram of this system is shown in figure. The major building blocks of this project are:

- ARM7(Advanced Risc Machine) 2138 microcontroller
- LCD (Liquid Crystal Display)
- Finger print module
- GSM 300
- MAX 232

CONCLUSION

E-License system will be the best invention which will defiantly helps in maintaining the centralized national database and again as the finger will act as a license it's not required to carry the license. It's also helps in reducing the corruption.

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